

The reason for the existence of the Stationary Action Principle

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12 August 2025

Abstract

Giving a specific value to the action S and its extremes t_1, t_2 , a "functional equation" is obtained. Its (in general) many solutions would imply the observation of a single body running simultaneously along many paths (all defined in $\Delta t = t_2 - t_1$). This is impossible and a single path is necessary. This is realized imposing $\delta S = 0$. So it is the "single path condition" to justify the Stationary Action Principle. With this condition some simple cases are analyzed. Also it doesn't appear in contradiction with quantum mechanics.

Introduction

The Stationary Action Principle can be obtained by Feynman's paths integral [1]: the most probable paths are those for which δS is small and equal to zero at the classical limit.

However with the "single path condition" (single solution), as experimentally observed and logically expected, a direct explanation about the Stationary Action Principle is obtained. We consider the Lagrangian of a single body, but a generalization concerning more complex cases appears natural. This approach could simplify many problems, in quantum mechanics too.

A logical reason

The action S is: $S(Q) = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} L(q(t), \dot{q}(t), t) dt$ (with Q the path $q(t)_{t_1, t_2}$ from q_1 to q_2), [3] [4] [5].

$L(q(t), \dot{q}(t), t)$, to have a physical meaning, is finite in the finite interval t_1, t_2 . And then S exists with a finite value, regardless of its possible physical meaning.

Giving a specific value to S and extremes t_1, t_2, q_1, q_2 , a "functional equation" is obtained:

$$\int_{t_01}^{t_02} L(q(t), \dot{q}(t), t) dt = S_0 \quad (1)$$

In general, for an arbitrary S value, many Lagrangians $L(Q)$, then many paths Q , are

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solutions of this equation and this is the fundamental reason to have considered the functional S .

These Lagrangians (equation solutions) are all equivalent to each other. In fact they cannot be physically distinguished to obtain a correct physical behavior, because each Lagrangian alone represents the entirely physical meaning and nothing else. A superior physical principle which is able to distinguish and choose Lagrangians shouldn't exist (and we admit it doesn't exist). So, we would have a system in which, observing a single body, many Lagrangians $L_{(Q)}$ and then many paths Q simultaneously would exist, all being defined in the same time-interval $\Delta t = t_2 - t_1$! This isn't logically (and physically) possible. A single body has to be observed running along a single path (otherwise many bodies are observed simultaneously). Then only a single path has to exist and this corresponds to a value S_0 accomplishing $\delta S = 0$ ($\delta S = 0$ implies a single path). It corresponds to a minimum, maximum or flex point in the functional S . This point is unique and coincides with the unique path Q_0 from t_1 to t_2 ; see Figure 1 (a schematic representation). We call the necessity of an unique physical solution the "single path condition".

Some important cases

To illustrate the "single path condition" (or unique solution) we consider the motion of a body in space from the point A to B , without a potential energy into the Lagrangian (no external forces). Given specific values to t_1, t_2 , we see that for constant body speeds module $v > \frac{AB}{\Delta t}$ there are many possible paths (infinite paths for an assigned v), but if it is $v = \frac{AB}{\Delta t}$ only a single path is possible: precisely the straight line \overline{AB} ; see Figure 2. So, it has to be $v = \frac{AB}{\Delta t}$ and the path is straight from A to B . Note that in this case $|\vec{v}| = cost$. is necessary to accomplish a single path. A Lagrangian including a potential energy would imply a more complex treatment with a $\vec{v}(t)$. Now, we give a value to v , but not to t_1, t_2 . The result is the same: a single path is possible only considering the straight line from A to B . $\Delta t (= \frac{AB}{v})$ is obtained and it is the smallest. So we have found the Fermat's principle (an application).

This case is very important and for clarity we explain it in slightly different way.

Figure 2:

So, given t_1, t_2, A, B , we ask ourselves: is it possible for a single-body the path from A (at t_1) to B (at t_2)? For $v = |\vec{v}| = \text{cost.} = \frac{AB}{\Delta t}$ the path is unique, the segment \overline{AB} . Higher speeds aren't allowed, in fact, many paths are possible simultaneously because they are all equivalent; space is homogeneous and isotropic, without any other conditions or presence of other bodies. Then a path can't be choose, they are all physically possible. If $|\vec{v}| \neq \text{cost.}$, a potential energy is necessary into the Lagrangian to accomplish a single path.

In the following other case we consider Fermat principle for light reflection law. This is solved with the "single path condition": given a value to t_1, t_2, A, C , a mirror and $|\vec{v}| = \text{cost.}$, there are many possible paths, but if it is $v = \frac{AB+BC}{\Delta t}$ only a single path is possible, with the angle $\widehat{\text{mirror}BA} = \widehat{\text{mirror}BC}$; see Figure 3. We have a similar consideration as before not giving a specific value to t_1, t_2 (Fermat principle).

Figure 3:

Fermat principle (minimum time) doesn't apply to a concave mirror; time is maximum [2]. But the "single path condition" is applicable. It is $\overline{AB} + \overline{BC}$; see Figure 4. However in this case it is necessary to consider that paths $\overline{AB}, \overline{AB'}, \overline{AB''}, \overline{BC}, \overline{B'C}, \overline{B''C}$ have to be straight lines, as deduced in the first case.

An half concave mirror seems to have no solution; see Figure 5. All paths (from A to C) for a given specific v are unique. But it is necessary to consider that all points (or at least some points?) of the path have to be consistent with the "single path condition", the path being real and observed. For example, the point B' in the mirror isn't consistent with points R and U belonging to the path $\overline{AB'} + \overline{B'C}$; the point in the mirror having to be approximately between R and U (in agreement with Fermat principle too). So, only the path $\overline{AB} + \overline{BC}$ is "locally" consistent and can

Figure 4:

exist. In practice we have had to use more information to find the unique solution.

Figure 5:

Coherence with quantum mechanics

Apparently, quantum mechanics, with probabilistic, many paths interpretation and above all an uncertain path, contradicts the "single path condition". But uncertainty could be interpreted as equivalent to a casual, "probabilistic" potential energy (existing but unknown) into the Lagrangian. Just think of observation by photons, like Heisenberg's microscope; a body undergoes variations of its momentum. In practice it is as if many potentials were possible and into the Lagrangian there was only one, even if we don't know it. And the solution is always the one for which the path is unique. In principle the same previous procedure is applied. Without forgetting that the observation requires a single path (collapse of the wave function). So, when uncertainty tends to zero, path tends to the classical one, but it is unique in any case.

References

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